

Synthesis of *N*-imino- β -lactams from 2,3-diaza-1,3-dienes (azines) mediated by POCl₃

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Abstract : Symmetrically substituted azines derived from aromatic aldehydes have been found compatible with the reaction of phenoxyacetic acid activated by POCl₃. *N*-Imino- β -lactams are efficiently obtained by this method in good to excellent yields with varying levels of *cis*, *trans*-selectivity.

Keywords : Azines, *N*-imino- β -lactams, stereoselectivity, cycloaddition.

The readily available 2,3-diaza-1,3-dienes (azines) have been used as templates for constructing fused heterocyclic systems because of their tendency to form cycloadducts in reactions with bifunctional nucleophilic agents¹. Their use in the synthesis of hydrazones² and heterocyclic compounds³ is also well-documented. However, their use in cycloaddition reaction is limited because they are less reactive as compared to 1,4-diaza-1,3-dienes^{4,5} which react smoothly with ketenes to yield 4-imino- β -lactams. The decreased reactivity for the azines can be attributed to the lone pair-lone pair interaction between the proximal nitrogens rendering the azine nitrogen less basic for their reaction with ketenes. In spite of these constraints, literature do report the synthesis of *N*-imino- β -lactams from azines with enolates⁶ as well as ketenes⁷.

Results and discussion

Keeping in view our success in preparing a variety of β -lactams using POCl₃ method^{8,9}, we thought of using this reagent taking azines as substrates for preparing *N*-imino- β -lactams. Various symmetrically substituted azines **2** were used for the present work, which could be easily procured¹⁰ in high yields (Scheme 1) from aromatic aldehydes **1** on reaction with hydrazine sulphate in the presence of aqueous ammonia and water.

Symmetrically substituted azines **2** were subjected to cycloaddition reaction with phenoxyacetic acid. This reac-

Entry	Compd.	Ar	Yield (%)
1	2a		94
2	2b		90
3	2c		92
4	2d		94
5	2e		80
6	2f		85
7	2g		87

Scheme 1

tion was carried out in refluxing benzene under nitrogen atmosphere in the presence of triethylamine, followed by dropwise addition of POCl₃ (Scheme 2).

N-Imino- β -lactams **3** were formed in good to excellent yields, with varying levels of *cis*, *trans*-selectivity (Table 1). The *cis* and *trans* stereoisomeric mixtures obtained were separated by using column chromatography on neutral alumina. The structures of all the *N*-imino- β -lactams **3** synthesized have been confirmed by spectral data (FT-IR, ¹H NMR).

Scheme 2

Table 1. Synthesis of *N*-imino- β -lactams 3 from azines 2 and phenoxyacetic acid

Entry	Compd.	Ar	<i>cis</i> : <i>trans</i> ^a	Yield ^b (%)	
				<i>cis</i>	<i>trans</i>
1	3a		55 : 45	59	25
2	3b		65 : 45	57	21
3	3c		16 : 84	5	80
4	3d		55 : 45	61	28
5	3e		85 : 15	62	4
6	3f		43 : 57	23	58
7	3g		33 : 67	7	51

^aDetermined by the integration of the signals corresponding to H₃-H₄ in the ¹H NMR spectra of the crude mixture. ^bRefers to pure, isolated products. All of them showed satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Experimental

All melting points (m.p. °C) are uncorrected. The FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. Only the principal peaks of interest are reported and expressed in cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Jeol AL 300 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts expressed as δ values (ppm) downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS). Thin layer chromatography was performed using TLC-grade silica gel (G) and was developed in an atmosphere of iodine vapours.

Typical procedure for the preparation of *N*-imino- β -lactams (3a-3g) :

To a refluxing solution of phenoxyacetic acid (1.8 mmol), azine (1.8 mmol) and triethylamine (6 mmol) in dry toluene, POCl₃ was added dropwise under nitrogen. Refluxing was done until whole azine got reacted (monitored by TLC). The reaction mixture was cooled and toluene was evaporated under reduced pressure and resulting residue was washed first with NaHCO₃ (10 mL) and then with water (3 \times 10 mL) and dried over anhy-

drous Na₂SO₄ to get *N*-imino- β -lactam 3. *cis* and *trans* isomers were separated by column chromatography (ethylacetate : hexane : 3 : 97).

1-(Benzylideneamino)-3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-azetidin-2-one (3a) : *cis*-Isomers : solid, m.p. 174 °C (Found : C, 77.05; H, 5.15; N, 8.48. C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 77.17; H, 5.30; N, 8.18%); IR : ν = 1777.4 cm⁻¹; β -lactam (C=O); ¹H NMR CDCl₃ (δ /ppm) : 5.36 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 5.39 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 6.71–7.56 (15H, m, ArH), 7.96 (1H, s, CH=N). *trans*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 120 °C; IR : ν = 1777.4 cm⁻¹; β -lactam (C=O); ¹H NMR CDCl₃ (δ /ppm) : 4.89 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 4.93 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 6.76–7.52 (15H, m, ArH), 8.01 (1H, s, CH=N).

1-(4-Methoxybenzylideneamino)-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-phenoxy-2-azetidinone (3b) : *cis*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 166 °C (Found : C, 71.45; H, 5.35; N, 7.05. C₂₄H₂₂N₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 71.63; H, 5.51; N, 6.96%); IR : ν = 1772.1 cm⁻¹; β -lactam (C=O); ¹H NMR CDCl₃ (δ /ppm) : 3.74 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.77 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.31 (1H, d, *J* 4.8 Hz), 5.34 (1H, d, *J* 4.8 Hz), 6.69–7.49 (13H, m, ArH), 7.82 (1H, s, CH=N). *trans*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 145 °C; IR : ν = 1772.1 cm⁻¹; β -lactam (C=O); ¹H NMR CDCl₃ (δ /ppm) : 3.77 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.89 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz), 4.93 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 6.74–7.77 (13H, m, ArH), 8.52 (1H, s, CH=N).

1-(4-Chlorobenzylideneamino)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-phenoxy-2-azetidinone (3c) : *trans*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 140 °C (Found : C, 64.05; H, 3.81; N, 6.92. C₂₂H₁₆Cl₂N₂O₄ calcd. for : 64.25; H, 3.92; N, 6.81%); IR : ν = 1782.4 cm⁻¹; β -lactam (C=O); ¹H NMR CDCl₃ (δ /ppm) : 4.92 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 4.98 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 6.78 (13H, m, ArH), 8.53 (1H, s, CH=N).

1-(2-Methylbenzylideneamino)-4-(2-methylphenyl)-3-phenoxy-2-azetidinone (3d) : *cis*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 152 °C (Found : C, 77.68; H, 5.78; N, 7.72. C₂₄H₂₂N₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 77.81; H, 5.99; N, 7.56%); IR : ν = 1776.1 cm⁻¹; β -lactam (C=O); ¹H NMR CDCl₃ (δ /ppm) : 2.16 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.23 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.42 (1H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 5.52 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 6.73–7.79 (13H, m, ArH), 8.18 (1H, s, CH=N). *trans*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 168 °C;

IR : $\nu = 1776.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; β -lactam (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR CDCl}_3$ (δ/ppm) : 2.15 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.36 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.91 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 5.24 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 6.87–7.77 (13H, m, ArH), 8.22 (1H, s, CH=N).

1-*{(Benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)methyleneamino}*-4-*(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)-3-phenoxyazetid-2-one (3e)* : *cis*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 153–154 °C (Found : C, 66.85; H, 4.15; N, 6.65. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$ calcd. for : C, 66.97; H, 4.22; N, 6.51%); IR : $\nu = 1774.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; β -lactam (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR CDCl}_3$ (δ/ppm) : 5.65 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz), 5.86 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz), 5.99 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.7–7.34 (11H, m, ArH), 8.46 (1H, s, CH=N).

1-*(2-Furfurylideneamino)-4-(2-furyl)-3-phenoxy-2-azetidione (3f)* : *cis*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 98 °C (Found : C, 66.98; H, 4.22; N, 8.53. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 67.07; H, 4.38; N, 8.69%); IR : $\nu = 1782.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; β -lactam (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR CDCl}_3$ (δ/ppm) : 5.39 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 5.42 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 6.25–7.64 (11H, m, ArH), 8.18 (1H, s, CH = N). *trans*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 136 °C; IR : $\nu = 1782.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; β -lactam (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR CDCl}_3$ (δ/ppm) : 5.02 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 5.23 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 6.38–7.64 (11H, m, ArH), 8.33 (1H, s, CH=N).

1-*{(Thiophen-2-yl)methyleneamino}*-3-phenoxy-4-*(thiophen-2-yl)azetid-2-one (3g)* : *trans*-Isomer : solid, m.p. 169–170 °C (Found : C, 60.75; H, 4.02; N, 7.78. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ calcd. for : C, 60.99; H, 3.98; N, 7.90%); IR : $\nu = 1779.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; β -lactam (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR CDCl}_3$

(δ/ppm) : 5.05 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 5.25 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 6.83–7.34 (11H, m, ArH), 8.35 (1H, s, CH=N).

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